

The Effectiveness of Using Duolingo for learning Vocabulary of English-majored students in HUFU

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Abstract

With the development of technology in the 4.0 industrial era, many software and apps are created in the market which is used for educational purposes. Using software and apps is an effective way to help students learning vocabulary easily and conveniently. One of the best apps is Duolingo- An effective app for learning vocabulary. This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of using Duolingo in learning vocabulary. A questionnaire consists of 10 questions that are used for 30 English-majored students in HUFU to answer. Then, evaluate the effectiveness based on the result of the questionnaire. The questionnaire's result gave an expected result that nearly 85% of students said that using Duolingo is effective, very convenient, and easy to learn vocabulary. Besides, learners are more motivated in learning vocabulary, help students learn vocabulary easily with many excited topics. This study may help the students find a suitable app to learn English in general and vocabulary in particular.

Keywords: Duolingo, Apps, Vocabulary, Method, Learning.

1. Introduction

An important thing about learning English is learning and mastering vocabulary. If learners cannot master their vocabulary, they often have some difficulty to understand the language and use it. Many researchers found that between vocabulary and grammar, vocabulary is more important. Carter & McCarthy (2014) stated that a person who masters vocabulary is a person who can use words and understand the meaning of them. Vocabulary is an important part of English. It is the basis for the development of four skills in English: Listening, Reading, Speaking, and Writing (UKEssays, 2016). In learning English, learners need to know about vocabulary if they want to use it or express their own ideas. Learners who lacks of vocabulary often have difficult to learn English and understand the meaning of words. Therefore, learners need to find a way to improve their vocabulary. Learning English vocabulary by using software and other apps is a good way, especially Duolingo. There are four reasons for learning English from software and apps: Convenience, economy, fun, and variety (Darlene, 2018). This study aims to help the student answer the question: Will Duolingo be effective? Can it help learners learning vocabulary? And decide on using this for learning vocabulary. Besides, with the implementation of this study, English learners can find an effective way to learn vocabulary or using this method together with the other method for the best result.

2. Literature review

2.1 The Nature of Vocabulary

a. The Definition of Vocabulary

Vocabulary is very important in the field of learning English. Richards & Renandya (2002) says that vocabulary is the basic elements of language. It proves for the learner's using language and how well learners speak, listen, read, and write. Without vocabulary and strategies to learn a new word, from making or use language learning opportunities around them such as listening to music, reading newspapers, using the language in daily life, or watching television (p.255). According to Nunan (1991), vocabulary is difficult to acquire in the learning process in the classroom. Vocabulary is the core of the English language because without vocabulary, learners cannot express their own ideas and cannot understand others. For instance, students often get difficulties in understanding the whole meaning of the text because they do not know the meaning of words in the text. In speaking, it is too hard to communicate with others when students just have a few vocabularies.

b. The Importance of Learning Vocabulary

Learners need to master vocabulary for improving other skills in English. Wilkins (1972) stated the importance of vocabulary that without grammar, maybe a little of information can be conveyed but without vocabulary, convey information is impossible. Indeed, vocabulary is very necessary and it is the starting of the English learning process. Therefore, learners need to find a way to learn vocabulary because of the important role of vocabulary.

c. The Way to Learn Vocabulary

There are many ways to learn vocabulary. In some traditional ways, learners memorize the word by writing it on the piece of paper (with the definitions), on small cards, or says the word many times and ask someone to test their speaking. Learners can divide words into different groups, some highlight the word that they look up in the dictionary. But all of the ways above are not effective enough. Today, with the spread of technology, many software, and mobile applications are created to help learners. One of the best ways to learn vocabulary is using Duolingo – an app that helps learners learning vocabulary.

2.2 Duolingo

a. The Definition of Duolingo

Duolingo or Multilingual is a free language learning application and website that are created to help learners to learn a new language. It can help learners easier to identify, understand the meaning of vocabulary, and memorize it. This app also gives learners more motivation, makes learners happy, interest and comfortable when using. Learners can use this app to learn English vocabulary too with many methods from flashcards to fun-game and especially, learners can use this app in both classroom and home. Duolingo can be used for all ages from children, teenagers to adults. Especially, there are various languages that learners can learn from this application such as Arabic, English, Germany, Spanish, French, Italian and Dutch In the future, Duolingo is being

used in teaching programs at some school because of its benefits and features. Gusano (2017) stated that learning a new language with an app is cost-saving, time-saving. Although there is plenty of software and mobile applications are used for education purposes, some learners cannot explore and use it for their study in general and for learning English vocabulary in particular because most learners think this way is not a good choice. This study will show the effectiveness of using Duolingo for learning English.

b. Advantages of Duolingo

Duolingo has lots of advantages. It is free language learning apps that can be used to help students improve vocabulary, motivate students to learn English with many amazing topics and vocabulary games. Duolingo also creates exercises for students to help them review and practice the lesson at home. Duolingo can be accessed anywhere. Therefore, students can learn English anytime and anywhere with Duolingo.

c. Disadvantages of Duolingo

Besides the benefit Duolingo brings to students, this application also has some disadvantages. The biggest disadvantage is that Duolingo is an online application. It means that when students want to use Duolingo, they must have an internet connection. Besides, teachers who want to use this app to teach their students in the classroom have to use the projector.

3. Method

3.1 Research design

The research design which is used in this study is evaluation. A questionnaire consists of 10 questions that are used for 30 English-majored students (who are using or used to use Duolingo for learning vocabulary) in HUFU to answer. The research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of using Duolingo to learn vocabulary through the result of a questionnaire.

3.2 Participants

The participants of the research is English-majored students in HUFU. They are using Duolingo for their vocabulary learning. There are 30 participants in total (12 male and 18 female). They are undergraduate students (15 freshman, ten students in second-year, four in third-year and one at fourth-year).

3.3 Questionnaire

The questionnaire consists of ten questions for 30 students at HUFU to answer. This questionnaire is used for evaluate the effectiveness of using Duolingo to learn vocabulary. There are eight questions used for ask about student's interest with Duolingo. Two questions used for ask students about disadvantages of using Duolingo to learn vocabulary. There are five options from one to five for students to choose: Strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree and strongly agree.

Table 1: Item 1 to Item 5

Table 2: Item 6 to Item 10

Data analysis procedures

Step 1: Making a questionnaire that is consists of 10 questions for 30 English-majored students at HUFU

Step 2: Giving the questionnaire to 30 students to answer

Step 3: Collecting data from the questionnaire

Step 4: Analyzing data by Microsoft Excel

3.4 Data analysis

Item 1: Duolingo was easy to use

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Agree</i>	20	66,67%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	10	33,33%
Total	30	100%

This item is used to ask students about the experience when using Duolingo. The table above shows that most of the students say Duolingo is very easy to use. There are 66,67% of students agree and 33,33% strongly agree. No one disagrees with this statement.

Item 2: The students feel more motivated to learn English by using Duolingo

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	1	3,33%
<i>Agree</i>	9	30%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	20	66,67%
Total	30	100%

From the table above, there are 30% agree that they feel more motivated in learning vocabulary with Duolingo. There are 66,67% of students strongly agree, and 3,33% neither agree nor disagree. This calculation shows that Duolingo gives students more

motivation to learn English and has a positive effect on students. Most of them feel motivated to learn by using Duolingo.

Item 3: Learning English by using Duolingo makes the students more skillful in memorizing vocabulary

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	3	10%
<i>Agree</i>	17	56,67%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	10	33,33%
Total	30	100%

Based on the table above, most of students said that using Duolingo helps them memorize vocabulary easily. There are 56,67% of students agree and 33,33% strongly agree.

Item 4: Learning with Duolingo provides an opportunity to be more active in learning vocabulary

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	3	10%
<i>Disagree</i>	2	6,67%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	2	6,67%
<i>Agree</i>	7	23,33%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	16	53,33%
Total	30	100%

Based on the data, there are 53,33% of students strongly agree and 23,33% agree that using Duolingo helps them be more active in learning vocabulary. There are a few students choose disagree. Therefore, Duolingo can give students more opportunity to learn vocabulary.

Item 5: Duolingo makes it difficult for students in understanding and practicing vocabulary.

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	10	33,33%
<i>Disagree</i>	15	50%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	5	16,67%
<i>Agree</i>	0	0%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	0	0%
Total	30	100%

The table above showed that almost the student disagrees with item number five. It means that Duolingo does not make difficult for student when using this application.

Item 6: Duolingo is less useful for learning vocabulary

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	14	46,67%
<i>Disagree</i>	3	10%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	6	20%
<i>Agree</i>	6	20%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	1	3,33%
Total	30	100%

Based on the table above, there are 56,67% of students thought that Duolingo is useful for learning vocabulary.

Item 7: Duolingo encouraged students to discover new ideas

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Disagree</i>	5	16,67%

<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	3	10%
<i>Agree</i>	15	50%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	7	23,33%
Total	30	100%

The table above shows that there are 73,33% of students said that Duolingo helps them come up with new ideas and 26,67% of students said Duolingo can not.

Item 8: Learning by using Duolingo get students in mastering new vocabulary.

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	2	6,67%
<i>Agree</i>	13	43,33%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	15	50%
Total	30	100%

Based on the data, there are 93,33% of students said that Duolingo helps students master vocabulary. Just a few student disagree. It means that Duolingo really helps learners learning vocabulary effectively.

Item 9: In my opinion, using Duolingo in learning is boring

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	10	33,33%
<i>Disagree</i>	8	26,67%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	10	33,33%
<i>Agree</i>	2	6,67%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	0	0%

Total 30 100%

Many of students disagree that using Duolingo in learning vocabulary is boring (33,33% of students strongly disagree and 26,67% of them disagree). Based on the result, Duolingo is not a boring language learning application.

Item 10: I am satisfied with Duolingo

Option	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Disagree</i>	0	0%
<i>Neither agree or disagree</i>	1	3,33%
<i>Agree</i>	6	20%
<i>Strongly Agree</i>	23	76,67%
Total	30	100%

The last item, there are 86,67% of students said that they feel satisfied when using Duolingo to learn vocabulary. Based on this result, Duolingo can bring to learners the best experience for their study.

4. Discussion

In this study, the writer use questionnaire to evaluate the effectiveness of using Duolingo for learning vocabulary. The purpose of this research is to know the experience of students who use Duolingo for their learning vocabulary, then evaluate the effect of using this application to learn vocabulary. The results of the questionnaire shows that nearly 85% of 30 participants said that Duolingo could help them to be more motivated, give them more opportunities in learning vocabulary. They enjoy learning with Duolingo. They can also practice their English in daily life. Most of students said that Duolingo has lots of benefits. Duolingo can help students master their vocabulary, encourage them to discover new ideas, and easy to memorize vocabulary. Besides, most of them also said that Duolingo is not a boring application. Based on this expected result, it can be concluded that Duolingo is an effective and interesting application for learning vocabulary because it has many positive effects that can help students master their vocabulary.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the result and discussion, the conclusion can be drawn as the following:

First, using Duolingo for learning vocabulary is a good idea. It can be proven by the result of the questionnaire that 85% of students agree that Duolingo has lots of benefits, it can help students master their vocabulary.

Second, with the implementation of this study, teachers can deciding on applying Duolingo to teach English in the classroom. And other students who confuse about using what method to learn vocabulary can choose Duolingo because it can help a lot.

5.2 Suggestion

After conducting evaluation research and analyzing the result of the questionnaire, the researcher found some suggestions that would be beneficial for students, teachers, and other researchers who are will using or studying about using Duolingo to learn vocabulary. Here are some suggestions:

- a. To make the lesson in class more effective, besides the traditional method of teaching, teachers should apply an application for their teaching. Using Duolingo is a good idea for teachers. This application helps students find new words, helps them learn new words easily, and help them understand the material, and also helps them memorize new words better.
- b. Duolingo will have students on mastering their vocabulary. Therefore, students should use this app for their learning because Duolingo is free and beneficial application. It does not only help them to learn vocabulary but also to use and practice vocabulary in their daily life.
- c. Other researchers can use this research as a reference for their research. Duolingo not only can be used for learning vocabulary of students but also used for teaching in the class of teachers and other activity in learning a new language.

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7. Appendix

Do you agree with the following statements?

1. Duolingo was easy to use.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree

- Strongly agree
- 2. The students feel more motivated to learn English by using Duolingo.**
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 3. Learning English by using Duolingo makes the students more skillful in memorizing vocabulary.**
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 4. Learning with Duolingo provides an opportunity to be more active in learning vocabulary.**
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 5. Duolingo makes it difficult for students in understanding and practicing vocabulary.**
- Strongly disagree
 - Disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Agree
 - Strongly agree
- 6. Duolingo is less useful for learning vocabulary.**
- Strongly disagree

- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

7. Duolingo encouraged students to discover new ideas.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

8. Learning by using Duolingo get students in mastering new vocabulary.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

9. In my opinion, using Duolingo in learning is boring.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

10. I am satisfied with Duolingo.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

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